

A Multi-Infrastructure OAI-PMH Endpoint for Research Infrastructure Orchestration in the H2IOSC Project

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Abstract. This paper presents the design and implementation of a multi-infrastructure OAI-PMH 2.0 endpoint developed within the H2IOSC project, an Italian initiative aimed at strengthening the digital infrastructure for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). The system enables multiple European research infrastructures – including OPERAS, E-RIHS, and CLARIN – to expose their resource metadata through a unified harvesting interface, supporting both Dublin Core and a custom native metadata format. We describe the complete system architecture, which comprises a web-based data entry application, a secured backend API, a Git-based data repository, and a fully compliant OAI-PMH server. A distinctive contribution of this work is the detailed description of the data lifecycle: how a single metadata field travels from the user interface, through the JSON data layer, to its final representation in the OAI-PMH XML response. The system has been validated against the official OpenArchives OAI-PMH validator and is currently in production use. The architecture is designed for replicability and can be adopted by other projects requiring multi-tenant metadata harvesting capabilities.

Keywords: OAI-PMH, H2IOSC, OPERAS, OPERAS-IT, research infrastructure, metadata harvesting, infrastructure orchestration, SSH, Social Sciences and Humanities, Dublin Core, interoperability

1. Introduction

The H2IOSC project (Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud) is a national infrastructure initiative funded within the Italian Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (PNRR). Its primary goal is to strengthen the digital infrastructure supporting Italian research in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), connecting national nodes of four European research infrastructures, CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it and OPERAS-IT.

A central component of the H2IOSC architecture is the Marketplace, a registry of tools, datasets, publications, services, and other scholarly resources contributed by the participating research infrastructures. The Italian nodes of OPERAS, E-RIHS, and CLARIN – each with distinct disciplinary focuses and data practices – need to describe, register, and expose their resources in a manner that is both infrastructure-specific and interoperable.

Within the OPERAS-IT work package, we proposed and implemented the concept of orchestrating the services developed by the participating infrastructures by exposing their metadata through the OAI-PMH 2.0 protocol (Lagoze et al., 2002). This approach allows a central harvester to collect resource descriptions from multiple infrastructures through a

single protocol, enabling unified discovery while preserving the autonomy of each contributing infrastructure.

This paper describes the complete technical implementation of the multi-infrastructure OAI-PMH endpoint. In addition to the system architecture and conformance analysis, we present a detailed account of the data lifecycle – from user input to protocol output – which we believe is a reusable contribution for any project facing similar interoperability challenges.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the overall system architecture. Section 3 presents the data lifecycle in detail, tracing how metadata fields are captured, stored, and exposed. Section 4 discusses OAI-PMH 2.0 conformance and validation. Section 5 addresses security considerations. Section 6 discusses replicability and conclusions.

2. System Architecture

The system is composed of five main components, each deployed independently and communicating through standard web protocols and the GitHub API (Fig.1).

Figure 1 - System architecture and data flow. The five main components are: Data Entry Web App (Cloudflare Pages), Backend API (Render), GitHub data repository (h2iosc-data), GitHub configuration repository (h2iosc-config), and OAI-PMH Server (Render). Solid arrows indicate the primary data flow from user input to OAI-PMH harvesting; the dashed arrow indicates API key verification. Each GitHub connection uses a dedicated fine-grained token with minimal permissions.

2.1 Data Entry Web Application

The data entry interface is a single-page HTML application served through Cloudflare Pages. It provides a tabbed interface for entering resource metadata organized according to the H2IOSC data model: items, properties, media, identities, actors, contacts, sources, and relations. Authentication is handled by Cloudflare Access, which provides email-based one-time-code verification before granting access to the application.

Figure 2 - The H2IOSC Data Entry System dashboard

The application operates entirely in the browser, storing work-in-progress data in the browser’s local storage. When the user is ready to submit, the data is serialized as a single JSON document and transmitted to the backend API.

2.2 Backend API

The backend API is a Python Flask application deployed on Render. It receives submissions from the data entry application, validates them against the H2IOSC data model schema, and writes the validated JSON document to the GitHub data repository through the GitHub Contents API.

Authentication is performed via API keys transmitted in the X-API-Key HTTP header. Each key is bound to a specific infrastructure and site, preventing cross-infrastructure data submission. Keys are stored in hashed form (SHA-256) and are not recoverable from the server. Rate limiting is enforced in memory to prevent abuse. Input validation includes both schema verification and path injection prevention through strict regular expression checks on infrastructure and site identifiers.

When a new submission is received, the backend first removes any existing JSON files in the target directory (`data/{infrastructure}/{site}/`) before writing the new file, ensuring that each infrastructure-site pair has exactly one current submission file.

2.3 Data Repository

The data repository is a private GitHub repository that serves as the persistent storage layer. Its directory structure reflects the organizational hierarchy of the project:

```

data/
├── operas/
│   └── roma/
│       └── 20260304_162000.json
├── erihis/
│   └── lecce/
│       └── 20260304_134205.json
└── clarin/

```

Each JSON file follows a standardized envelope structure containing a *data* object (with arrays for items, properties, media, identities, actors, contacts, sources, and relations) and a *metadata* object (with infrastructure identifier, site, timestamp, and schema version).

This approach leverages GitHub as a versioned, audit-trailed data store. Every modification is recorded as a Git commit, providing complete traceability of data changes without requiring a dedicated database infrastructure.

2.4 OAI-PMH Server

The OAI-PMH server is a Python Flask application deployed on a separate Render instance. It reads data from the GitHub repository through the GitHub Contents API using a read-only access token, processes the JSON files, and serves responses conforming to the OAI-PMH 2.0 protocol.

The server operates as a multi-tenant endpoint. Each infrastructure is accessible at a dedicated URL path (e.g., /operas/, /erihs/), and the root path (/) serves a portal page listing all active infrastructures with their record counts. The server supports all six OAI-PMH verbs and two metadata formats: Dublin Core (oai_dc) and a custom H2IOSC native format (h2iosc).

3. The Data Lifecycle

A distinctive aspect of this implementation is the transformation pipeline that metadata fields undergo from user input to protocol output. In this section, we trace this lifecycle using two representative examples of increasing complexity.

3.1 Simple Field: Resource Name

The H2IOSC data model requires resource names to be provided in both Italian and English. We trace the *name* field through all four stages.

Stage 1: HTML form. The data entry application presents two input fields:

```
<input type="text" id="item-name-it" placeholder="Nome in italiano">
<input type="text" id="item-name-en" placeholder="Name in English">
```

Stage 2: JSON storage. When the user submits, the values are stored as flat fields within the item object:

```
{
  "data": {
    "items": [{
      "id": "operas-roma-item-001",
      "nameIT": "NormaTEI",
      "nameEN": "NormaTEI",
      "type": "tool",
      "uri": "https://github.com/pierpaolosichera/NormaTEI"
    }]
  }
}
```

Stage 3: OAI-PMH native format (h2iosc). The OAI-PMH server transforms the flat JSON fields into a namespaced, multilingual XML structure:

```

<h2iosc:item xmlns:h2iosc="http://h2iosc.org/h2iosc/item/">
  <h2iosc:name>
    <h2iosc:value h2iosc:language="en">NormaTEI</h2iosc:value>
    <h2iosc:value h2iosc:language="it">NormaTEI</h2iosc:value>
  </h2iosc:name>
</h2iosc:item>

```

Stage 4: OAI-PMH Dublin Core (oai_dc). For the Dublin Core mapping, the name is mapped to the `dc:title` element. If both language versions are available, the English version is used as primary title:

```

<oai_dc:dc xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/">
  <dc:title>NormaTEI</dc:title>
</oai_dc:dc>

```

This four-stage transformation illustrates a general pattern: the HTML layer captures language-specific values as separate fields; the JSON layer stores them as flat key-value pairs (nameIT, nameEN); the native OAI-PMH format restructures them into a semantically rich, multilingual XML schema; and the Dublin Core mapping reduces them to standardized, interoperable metadata elements.

3.2 Complex Field: Actor with Identity

A more complex case involves actors associated with items. In the H2IOSC data model, an actor is the combination of a role (e.g., author, curator) and an identity (a person or organization with associated contacts and external identifiers). This data is distributed across four separate data entry tabs in the application and must be reassembled during processing.

Stage 1: HTML forms. The user enters data across multiple tabs:

- *Identities tab*: creates an identity with a local ID, a type (person/organization/infrastructure), a label in Italian and English, and an optional external identifier (e.g., ORCID).
- *Contacts tab*: associates contact information (email, URL, phone) with an identity.
- *Sources tab*: associates external identifiers (ORCID, Wikidata, etc.) with an identity.
- *Actors tab*: binds an identity to an item with a specific role.

Stage 2: JSON storage. Each tab produces a separate array in the JSON document. The relationship between them is maintained through identifier references:

```

{
  "data": {
    "identities": [{
      "id": "operas-roma-ps",
      "type": "person",
      "labelIT": "Pierpaolo Sichera",
      "labelEN": "Pierpaolo Sichera",
      "externalId": "0000-0003-2157-7717"
    }],
    "contacts": [{
      "identityId": "operas-roma-ps",
      "type": "website",
      "value": "https://github.com/pierpaolosichera",
      "labelEN": "GitHub Repository"
    }],
  }
}

```

```

    }],
    "sources": [{
      "identityId": "operas-roma-ps",
      "type": "orcid",
      "id": "0000-0003-2157-7717"
    }],
    "actors": [{
      "itemId": "operas-roma-item-001",
      "identityId": "operas-roma-ps",
      "role": "author"
    }]
  }
}
}

```

Stage 3: OAI-PMH native format (h2iosc). The OAI-PMH server performs a join operation: for each item, it resolves actor references to identities, and for each identity, it resolves contact and source references. The result is a deeply nested XML structure:

```

<h2iosc:actors>
  <h2iosc:actor>
    <h2iosc:role>author</h2iosc:role>
    <h2iosc:identity>
      <h2iosc:externalId>0000-0003-2157-7717</h2iosc:externalId>
      <h2iosc:type>person</h2iosc:type>
      <h2iosc:label>
        <h2iosc:value h2iosc:language="en">Pierpaolo Sichera</h2iosc:value>
        <h2iosc:value h2iosc:language="it">Pierpaolo Sichera</h2iosc:value>
      </h2iosc:label>
      <h2iosc:contacts>
        <h2iosc:contact>
          <h2iosc:type>website</h2iosc:type>
          <h2iosc:label>
            <h2iosc:value h2iosc:language="en">GitHub Repository</h2iosc:value>
          </h2iosc:label>
          <h2iosc:value>https://github.com/pierpaolosichera</h2iosc:value>
        </h2iosc:contact>
      </h2iosc:contacts>
      <h2iosc:sources>
        <h2iosc:source>
          <h2iosc:id>0000-0003-2157-7717</h2iosc:id>
          <h2iosc:type>orcid</h2iosc:type>
        </h2iosc:source>
      </h2iosc:sources>
    </h2iosc:identity>
  </h2iosc:actor>
</h2iosc:actors>

```

Stage 4: OAI-PMH Dublin Core. The rich identity information is reduced to a single `dc:creator` element, using the identity's label as the creator name:

```

<dc:creator>Pierpaolo Sichera</dc:creator>

```

This example illustrates the denormalization that occurs during OAI-PMH serialization: data that is stored in a normalized, relational structure in JSON (four separate arrays with foreign key references) is reassembled into a deeply nested, self-contained XML representation for

each record. This design ensures that each OAI-PMH record is independently interpretable by a harvester without requiring additional API calls.

3.3 Generalization

The pattern described above applies to all fields in the H2IOSC data model. Table 1 summarizes the mapping for the principal field categories.

Field Category	HTML Input	JSON Structure	h2iosc XML	Dublin Core
Name	Two text inputs (IT, EN)	nameIT, nameEN	h2iosc:name with multilingual h2iosc:value	dc:title
Description	Two textareas (IT, EN)	shortDescriptionIT/EN	h2iosc:shortDescription with multilingual value	dc:description
Type	Select dropdown	type (string)	h2iosc:type	dc:type
URI	Text input	uri (string)	h2iosc:uri	dc:identifier
Keywords	Vocabulary selector	properties[] with propertyCode="keyword"	h2iosc:properties/property	dc:subject
Language	Vocabulary selector	properties[] with propertyCode="language"	h2iosc:properties/property	dc:language
License	Vocabulary selector	properties[] with propertyCode="license"	h2iosc:properties/property	dc:rights
Media	URL + MIME type inputs	media[] (separate array)	h2iosc:medias/media	-
Actors	Role + Identity selector	actors[] + identities[] (join on identityId)	h2iosc:actors/actor/identity (nested)	dc:creator

Table 1 - Field mapping summary

4. OAI-PMH 2.0 Conformance

4.1 Protocol Implementation

The server implements all six verbs defined by the OAI-PMH 2.0 specification:

- **Identify:** returns repository metadata including repository name, base URL, protocol version, administrator email, earliest datestamp, deleted record policy (set to “no”), and granularity (YYYY-MM-DD).
- **ListMetadataFormats:** advertises two supported metadata formats – oai_dc (Dublin Core) and h2iosc (native format).
- **ListSets:** returns a *noSetHierarchy* error, as the repository does not implement set-based organization. Each infrastructure is instead exposed as a separate OAI-PMH endpoint.
- **ListIdentifiers:** returns headers (identifier and datestamp) for all records matching the specified metadata prefix and optional date range filters.
- **ListRecords:** returns complete records with metadata for all matching records.
- **GetRecord:** returns a single record by its identifier.

4.2 Parameter Validation

The server performs comprehensive parameter validation as required by the specification:

- Date parameters (*from*, *until*) are validated against the YYYY-MM-DD format. Requests with datetime granularity (YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssZ) are rejected with *badArgument*, as the repository declares day-level granularity.
- Mixed granularity between *from* and *until* parameters is detected and rejected.
- The *resumptionToken* parameter is recognized as exclusive: if present with other parameters, a *badArgument* error is returned; if present alone, a *badResumptionToken* error is returned, as the current implementation does not support pagination (all records are returned in a single response).
- Unexpected parameters for each verb are detected and rejected.
- Both HTTP GET and POST request methods are supported.

4.3 Validation Results

The implementation has been validated against the official OpenArchives OAI-PMH validator (<https://www.openarchives.org/Register/ValidateSite>). The validation confirms correct behavior for all protocol verbs, proper error handling, and correct use of HTTP response codes.

Figure 3 - Screenshot of the OpenArchives validation results showing all tests passed

4.4 Multi-Infrastructure Design

A distinctive aspect of this implementation is the multi-tenant architecture. Rather than deploying separate OAI-PMH servers for each infrastructure, a single server instance handles all infrastructures through URL-based routing:

- <https://h2iosc-oaipmh.onrender.com/operas/> – OPERAS endpoint
- <https://h2iosc-oaipmh.onrender.com/erihhs/> – E-RIHS endpoint
- <https://h2iosc-oaipmh.onrender.com/clarin/> – CLARIN endpoint

Each endpoint behaves as an independent OAI-PMH repository with its own Identify response, record set, and base URL. Adding a new infrastructure requires only adding an entry to a configuration dictionary in the server code:

```
INFRASTRUCTURES = {  
    'operas': {
```

```

        'display': 'OPERAS',
        'full': 'OPERAS Infrastructure',
        'github_folder': 'data/operas'
    },
    # Adding a new infrastructure:
    'new_infra': {
        'display': 'NEW-INFRA',
        'full': 'New Infrastructure Name',
        'github_folder': 'data/new_infra'
    },
}

```

5. Security Considerations

The system implements multiple security layers appropriate for a research data infrastructure.

Authentication and authorization. The data entry application is protected by Cloudflare Access, which provides email-based authentication with one-time codes. The backend API uses infrastructure-specific API keys, stored only in hashed form (SHA-256) on the server. Each API key is bound to a specific infrastructure and site, enforcing strict data isolation.

Input validation. Infrastructure and site identifiers are validated against a strict regular expression pattern ($^[a-z0-9][a-z0-9_-]*$$) to prevent path traversal attacks. Submission data is validated against the H2IOSC data model schema before being accepted.

Access control. The system uses the principle of least privilege for GitHub access tokens. The OAI-PMH server uses a read-only token scoped to the data repository, while the backend API uses a write-enabled token scoped to the same repository. Neither token has access to the source code repositories.

Network isolation. Cross-Origin Resource Sharing (CORS) is restricted to the data entry application's domain, preventing unauthorized web applications from making requests to the backend API. Rate limiting is enforced in memory to prevent abuse.

Data integrity. The use of a Git repository as the storage layer provides a complete, immutable audit trail of all data modifications, with commit-level traceability of every change.

6. Replicability and Conclusions

6.1 Replicability

The architecture described in this paper is designed to be replicable by other projects with similar requirements. The entire system can be deployed using free-tier services:

- Cloudflare Pages (free tier) for static web application hosting with authentication
- Render (free tier) for Python application hosting
- GitHub (free private repositories) for data storage

No database server, dedicated hosting, or commercial infrastructure is required. The total operational cost of the system as deployed is zero.

The multi-tenant design means that a single deployment can serve multiple infrastructures or projects. The separation between the data model (defined in JSON) and the protocol layer (OAI-PMH XML) allows adaptation to different metadata schemas without modifying the protocol implementation.

6.2 Current Status and Future Work

The system is currently deployed and operational, serving metadata from the OPERAS and E-RIHS infrastructures within the H2IOSC project. The OAI-PMH endpoint has been validated against the official OpenArchives validator and is being harvested by the project's central marketplace.

Future development directions include: implementing pagination through `resumptionToken` for repositories with large numbers of records; adding selective harvesting through OAI-PMH sets (e.g., by resource type or site); integrating Cloudflare Access JWT tokens for end-to-end authentication; and developing a formal XSD schema for the h2iosc metadata format.

6.3 Conclusions

This paper has presented a complete, production-ready implementation of a multi-infrastructure OAI-PMH endpoint for the H2IOSC project. The key contributions are: (1) a replicable architecture for multi-tenant OAI-PMH serving using exclusively free-tier cloud services; (2) a detailed description of the data lifecycle from web form to protocol output, applicable as a reference pattern for similar systems; and (3) a fully conformant OAI-PMH 2.0 implementation supporting both standard Dublin Core and a custom metadata format.

The system demonstrates that standards-based interoperability between heterogeneous research infrastructures can be achieved with modest technical resources, provided that careful attention is paid to data modeling and protocol compliance.

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